

Abstract

Does Acupuncture Influence Melatonin Levels in Insomnia?

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Abstract

Introduction: Insomnia involves difficulty falling or staying asleep despite adequate rest and is linked to increased health risks. Around 10% of adults have chronic insomnia, with women, older adults, and socioeconomically disadvantaged groups being more affected. Melatonin, produced by the pineal gland, controls the body's sleep-wake cycle. Targeting melatonin may improve insomnia treatments. Traditional Chinese Medicine uses acupuncture to balance bodily systems and promote health. Studies show acupuncture can effectively treat sleep disorders, sometimes better than medication. We aim to determine if acupuncture influences melatonin levels in insomnia.

Methodology: PICO framework—patients with insomnia (population), acupuncture (intervention), any control group, melatonin levels as the primary outcome—a PubMed search was conducted. MeSH words were “Acupuncture AND insomnia AND melatonin,” filtered to include randomised controlled trials (RCTs) published in the last ten years. Inclusion criteria: studies that investigated acupuncture's effects on melatonin in insomnia; Exclusion criteria: studies measuring melatonin outside insomnia. Two researchers independently screened and extracted data, resolving disagreements through a third researcher to ensure consensus.

Results: 7 met the inclusion criteria. According to our results, melatonin levels increased after acupuncture treatment in five of the seven studies. However, results are limited by factors such as small sample sizes, diverse participant populations and related conditions (including pregnant women, cancer patients, students, and older adults), varied acupuncture protocols, and inconsistent measurement methods.

Conclusion: Acupuncture is a promising treatment option for insomnia, potentially mediated by an increase in melatonin levels. However, more well-designed studies are necessary to confirm its effectiveness.

Keywords: Insomnia; Melatonin; Acupuncture; Traditional Chinese Medicine.

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